

Phytochemical Profiling and Anti-Angiogenic Activity of *Antidesma bunius* (L.) Spreng Using the Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) Assay With ImageJ-Based Quantification

Yuanne T. Geyrozaga¹, Kierby John T. Erecilla², Ruzmien Eve L. Casuyon³, Joel Jr. C. Arcas⁴, Cleint Jaimon C. Perez⁵, Arianne V. Sepe⁶, Preciouskrizz S. Dutaro⁷, and Paul John A. Plecis, PhD⁸

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7}Senior High School Students, Silway-8 National High School, Polomolok, South Cotabato

⁸Senior High School Teacher, Silway-8 National High School, Polomolok, South Cotabato

Abstract

Cancer remains the second leading cause of mortality in the Philippines, underscoring the urgent need for novel and effective therapeutic agents. In recent years, natural plant-derived compounds have gained increasing attention due to their diverse bioactive properties and potential in drug discovery. *Antidesma bunius* (L.) Spreng., commonly known as Bignay, is a tropical plant widely distributed in Southeast Asia, particularly in the Philippines, and has been traditionally utilized for its medicinal and nutritional value.

This study aimed to evaluate the phytochemical composition of the ethanolic root extract of *A. bunius* and assess its anti-angiogenic activity using a duck embryo model. Preliminary phytochemical screening of the root extract revealed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, phenolics, saponins, steroids, and terpenoids, classes of compounds known to exhibit various biological activities, including modulation of angiogenic processes. A total of 25 fertilized duck eggs were allocated into five treatment groups. Following incubation, the embryos were harvested, documented, and analyzed using ImageJ software to quantify vascular development.

Results demonstrated a marked reduction in blood vessel formation in extract-treated groups compared to the negative control (distilled water) and the positive control (simvastatin), indicating a significant anti-angiogenic effect. These findings suggest that the ethanolic root extract of *A. bunius* possesses promising anti-angiogenic properties, highlighting its potential as a source of bioactive compounds for therapeutic applications in conditions characterized by abnormal vascular proliferation, such as cancer. Further studies are recommended to isolate and characterize the active constituents and the underlying molecular mechanisms of action.

Keywords: Anti-Angiogenic, *Antidesma bunius* (L.) Spreng, Angiogenesis, Cancer, Phytochemical Constituents

Introduction

Cancer remains a major global health concern, accounting for approximately 10 million deaths worldwide in 2020 (World Health Organization, 2022). In the Philippines, it is the second leading cause of mortality, with more than 66,000 deaths reported in the same year by the Department of Health (2023). Beyond its health impact, cancer imposes a substantial economic burden, with an estimated annual loss of ₱35 billion due to premature mortality,

particularly among individuals in their most productive years. These statistics highlight the urgent need for accessible, effective, and sustainable therapeutic strategies. One of the fundamental processes in tumor progression is angiogenesis, the formation of new blood vessels from pre-existing vasculature (Folkman, 1971; Carmeliet, 2005). This process enables tumors to acquire essential nutrients and oxygen, facilitating their growth, invasion, and metastasis (Hanahan & Weinberg, 2011). Consequently, targeting angiogenesis has become a critical strategy in cancer therapy. Despite advancements in anti-angiogenic treatments, commonly used synthetic drugs such as Bevacizumab and Sunitinib remain limited by high cost, adverse side effects, and the eventual development of drug resistance (Jayson et al., 2016; Ferrara & Adamis, 2016; Bergers & Hanahan, 2008). These limitations underscore the need to explore alternative therapeutic agents that are safer, more affordable, and biologically sustainable.

Plant-derived compounds have garnered increasing attention due to their structural diversity and wide range of pharmacological activities (Newman & Cragg, 2020). *Antidesma bunius* (L.) Spreng., commonly known as Bignay, is a tropical plant native to Southeast Asia and widely distributed in the Philippines. *A. bunius* has been reported to exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory activities (Butkhup & Samappito, 2011; Zaman et al., 2015). Despite these promising findings, research on the anti-angiogenic properties of *A. bunius* remains limited. Existing studies have focused on the leaves and fruits, leaving the roots largely unexplored. Addressing these gaps is essential for a more comprehensive evaluation of the therapeutic potential of *A. bunius*. This study aims to determine phytochemical constituents and antiangiogenic activity of *A. bunius* root extract using the CAM assay.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What phytochemical constituents, namely, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenolic, saponins, steroids, tannins, and terpenoids, are present in the *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng root ethanolic extract?
2. Does *A. bunius* (L.) Does Spreng root ethanolic extract exhibit anti-angiogenic activity in terms of the number of blood vessels, length of blood vessels, branching points, blood vessel area (%), blood vessel density, and average vessel diameter across the different treatments?
3. Is there a significant difference in the anti-angiogenic activity of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng based on the blood-vessel parameters across the treatment groups?

Methodology

Preparation of Plant Materials

The roots of *A. bunius* were collected from the data source in South Cotabato. It was washed thoroughly with tap water to remove soil and debris, air-dried at room temperature for 7 - 10 days, and then oven-dried at 40 - 45 degrees Celsius until the constant weight was achieved. The dried roots were pulverized into coarse powder using a mechanical grinder and stored in clean airtight containers. Approximately 500 grams of powdered sample was soaked in 95% ethanol for 72 hours with occasional stirring, followed by filtration through Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated on a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 40 °C to yield a crude ethanol extract, which was weighed and stored at 4 °C.

Qualitative Phytochemical Screening

For the photochemical screening, a portion of the crude extract was subjected to standard qualitative tests.

For **alkaloids**, 2 mL of extract was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, then divided into two test tubes: one was treated with Mayer's reagent (potassium mercuric iodide), where a cream or white precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids; the other was treated with Dragendorff's reagent (potassium bismuth iodide), where an orange or reddish-brown precipitated that confirm alkaloids. For **flavonoids**, about 2 mL of the extract solution was made by adding a few drops of hydrochloric acid and adding 2 pieces of magnesium ribbon; a change of color to orange, red, pink, or purple indicates the presence of flavonoids. For **glycosides**, the Keller-Killiani test was employed: 2 mL of extract was mixed with 1 mL of glacial acetic acid containing one drop of ferric chloride solution, then carefully underlaid with concentrated sulfuric acid; the formation of a brown ring at the interface indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides.

For **phenolics**, 2 mL of extract was treated with 3–4 drops of 5% ferric chloride solution; a blue, green, or black coloration indicated phenolic compounds. For **saponins**, the froth test was carried out by vigorously shaking 2 mL of extract with 5 mL of distilled water in a test tube; the persistence of stable froth for at least 15 minutes indicated the presence of saponins. For **steroids**, the Liebermann– Burchard test was conducted: 2 mL of extract was mixed with 2 mL of acetic anhydride and carefully underlaid with concentrated sulfuric acid; the appearance of a blue-green color confirms steroids. For **tannins**, 2 mL of extract was treated with a few drops of 5% ferric chloride solution, where a greenish-black or bluish black coloration indicated hydrolysable tannins, while the gelatin test was also performed by adding 1% gelatin solution containing sodium chloride to the extract, with a white precipitate indicating tannins. For **terpenoids**, the Salkowski test was applied: 2 mL of extract was mixed with 2 mL of chloroform, and concentrated sulfuric acid was carefully added to form a layer; a reddish-brown coloration at the interface indicated the presence of terpenoids.

Chorioallantoic Membrane Assay with ImageJ Quantification

For the anti-angiogenic assay, fertilized duck eggs were procured from a commercial hatchery and incubated at 37 ± 1 °C with 60–70% relative humidity in an incubator. Eggs were candled on day 3 to confirm viability, and only viable embryos were included in the study. A total of 25 eggs was randomly distributed into five treatment groups: T₁ (negative control, 0.1% DMSO in sterile distilled water), T₂ (positive control, Simvastatin 50 ppm), T₃ (*A. bunius* root extract 100 ppm), T₄ (*A. bunius* root extract 500 ppm), and T₅ (*A. bunius* root extract 1000 ppm), with 5 replicates per group.

On embryonic day 7, a small window (1–2 cm²) was aseptically created on the eggshell directly above the air sac using a rotary drill, exposing the Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM). Sterile filter paper discs (5 mm diameter) were impregnated with 200 µL of the assigned treatment solution and carefully placed onto the CAM surface using sterile forceps. The window was then sealed with sterile parafilm, and the eggs were returned to the incubator for 48–72 hours. At the endpoint, the eggs were reopened, and CAMs were photographed in situ using a stereomicroscope equipped with a digital camera at standardized magnification

(40x). Three image fields per CAM were captured around the treated site. Images were coded to ensure blinding and analyzed using ImageJ software. Vessel parameters measured included the number of blood vessels, total vessel length (μm), number of branching points, blood vessel area percentage (%), vessel density, and average vessel diameter (μm).

The captured CAM images were analyzed using ImageJ (NIH, USA). Each image was first coded to ensure blinding and calibrated with the stereomicroscope scale bar using the "Set Scale" function, so that all measurements were expressed in micrometers. The images were then converted to 8-bit grayscale, and the background contrast was enhanced to highlight the vessels. Uneven illumination was corrected using the "Subtract Background" function. To isolate the blood vessels, a global threshold was applied using either the Default or Otsu method, after which the image was binarized. The binarized images were then skeletonized, and the "Analyze Skeleton (2D/3D)" plugin was used to determine total vessel length, number of branches, and endpoints. Before skeletonization, the vessel area was measured using the "Analyze Particles" function, and the vessel density was calculated as the percentage of vessel area relative to the total CAM area in the field. The average vessel diameter was determined by dividing the vessel area by the total vessel length. For each CAM, three non-overlapping fields of view around the treatment disc were analyzed, and the mean values of all parameters were recorded per egg. The resulting data was exported into Excel for tabulation and subjected to statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, such as the mean, were computed for each treatment group to summarize the data. To determine significant differences in the anti-angiogenic activity across groups, the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality testing and Levene's statistic for the homogeneity test were used to determine whether the data set follows the assumption of the normal distribution pattern and equal variances. If the data is not normal and/or not homogenous, the Welch ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis Test was used. If the data is normal and homogeneous, the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed at a 0.01 level of significance. Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 27, and the results were presented in tables to illustrate the comparative effects of the treatments.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical standards for research involving biological materials. The plant material of *A. bunius* was collected responsibly, ensuring that proper identification and documentation were carried out, and collection was limited to prevent ecological harm. For the anti-angiogenic assay, fertilized duck eggs were used, which are generally considered to have minimal ethical concerns compared to vertebrate animal models, as the Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) assay does not involve fully developed sentient organisms. Eggs were handled under sterile conditions to reduce unnecessary embryo loss, and all procedures were conducted in compliance with institutional biosafety and laboratory safety protocols. Non-viable or terminated embryos were disposed of following proper biohazard waste management procedures.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative Phytochemical Profiling of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng

The qualitative phytochemical profiling of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng is essential for identifying the bioactive constituents that may contribute to its pharmacological potential. Characterizing these compounds provides a biochemical basis for their observed therapeutic properties, particularly in relation to anti-angiogenic activities. Table 1 summarizes the results of the preliminary phytochemical screening, highlighting the presence of key secondary metabolites detected in the plant extract.

Table 1. *Phytochemical Constituents of A. bunius* (L.) Spreng

Phytochemical Constituents	Test Results
Alkaloids (Mayer's reagent)	-
Alkaloids (Dragendorff's reagent)	+
Glycosides (Keller-Killiani test)	+
Phenolic (Ferric chloride test)	+
Saponins (Froth test)	+
Steroids (Liebermann-Burchard test)	+
Tannins (Ferric chloride & gelatin tests)	-
Terpenoids (Salkowski test)	+

Table 1 presented that *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng contains a diverse range of bioactive secondary metabolites. The ethanolic root extract tested positive for alkaloids (via Dragendorff's reagent), cardiac glycosides, phenolic compounds, saponins, steroids, and terpenoids, indicating their presence in the sample. In contrast, tannins were not detected under the conditions employed. The qualitative phytochemical screening confirms the presence of key bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, phenolics, diterpenes, and saponins. Phenolic compounds and flavonoids are known to have strong antioxidant properties contributing to the neutralization of free radicals and modulation of oxidative stress (Rice-Evans et al., 1997; Dai & Mumper, 2010). Saponins and terpenoids have been associated with antiproliferative and anti-inflammatory activities, while alkaloids are known for their cytotoxic and anticancer properties (Wink, 2015).

These findings are consistent with previous studies. For instance, Geronimo et al. (2015) reported similar metabolites in *A. bunius* leaf extracts, which exhibited notable antioxidant and cytotoxic activities against lung and colorectal cancer cell lines. Likewise, Jorjong et al. (2015) identified phenolic and flavonoid compounds in *A. bunius* fruit cultivars with significant antioxidant capacity. The presence of these phytochemicals is particularly relevant given their established roles in cancer-related mechanisms. Flavonoids and phenolic compounds are known to modulate oxidative stress and inhibit tumorigenesis, while saponins and diterpenes exhibit antiproliferative and pro-apoptotic effects across various cancer models.

Antiangiogenic Property of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng Across Blood Vessel Parameters

Angiogenesis is the process of the formation of blood vessels from pre-existing vasculature, which is a critical process in tumor growth and metastasis. Plant-derived compounds have shown potential in inhibiting this process due to their bioactive

constituents. Table 2 presents the antiangiogenic properties of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng across the specific blood vessel parameters such as number, length, branching points, blood vessel area, blood vessel density, and average vessel diameter across treatments.

Table 2. Anti-angiogenic Activity of *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng in Different Blood Vessel Parameters Across Treatments

Treatment	Blood Vessel Parameters (n=5)					
	Number of blood vessels (Count)	Length of blood vessels (mm)	Number of branching points (count)	Blood vessel area (%)	Blood vessel density	Average vessel diameter (μm)
T ₁ - dH ₂ O	395.40	14.46	225.40	6.72	0.170	2.38
T ₂ - Simvastatin	169.20	5.56	111.80	4.02	0.007	1.40
T ₃ - 100 ppm	248.00	10.76	160.20	4.44	0.009	2.27
T ₄ - 500 ppm	221.80	3.23	91.60	3.34	0.007	1.23
T ₅ - 1000 ppm	56.40	2.48	35.00	1.41	0.003	0.30

Table 2 demonstrates that *A. bunius* (L.) Spreng exhibits notable antiangiogenic activity across multiple blood vessel parameters. The negative control (T₁-dH₂O) showed the highest values in vessel count (395.40), vessel length (14.46 mm), branching points (225.40), and vessel area (6.72%), indicating extensive vascular development under normal conditions. In contrast, the positive control, Simvastatin (T₂), established an antiangiogenic effect in vessel length (5.56 mm), branching (111.80), and vessel density (0.007). Across the *A. bunius* treatments, a dose-dependent inhibition of angiogenesis was evident. The 100 ppm (T₃) and 500 ppm (T₄) treatments showed moderate reductions in vascular parameters compared to the control, indicating partial inhibition of blood vessel formation. Notably, the 1000 ppm treatment (T₅) exhibited the most pronounced effect, with the lowest values across all parameters, including vessel count (56.40), length (2.48 mm), branching points (35.00), vessel area (1.41%), and density (0.003). The consistent decrease in vessel number, length, branching, and density with increasing concentration suggests that *A. bunius* extract suppresses angiogenic processes.

These findings may be attributed to the presence of multiple bioactive phytochemicals, including phenolics, flavonoids, and other antioxidant compounds, which are known to exert biological activities through mechanisms such as antioxidant and redox modulation (Jorjong et al., 2015). Also, the reduction in the number of blood vessels indicates inhibition of angiogenic initiation, likely through suppression of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-mediated endothelial cell proliferation, which is a key driver of new vessel formation (Ferrara, 2004; Folkman, 1971). These findings demonstrate that *A. bunius* exerts a multi-targeted inhibitory effect on angiogenesis and has combined effects on vessel formation, elongation, branching, and network density.

The raw and skeletonized images (Figure 1) provide a visual representation of the vascular architecture across treatments, enabling qualitative assessment of angiogenic responses and supporting the quantitative analysis of blood vessel parameters. The raw images illustrate the overall density, distribution, and complexity of blood vessels. In

contrast, the skeletonized images highlight the structural framework of the vascular network by emphasizing vessel segments and branching patterns. This complementary visualization facilitates clearer comparison among treatments and enhances the reliability of measurements obtained through image analysis.

Figure 1. Representative raw and skeletonized vascular networks in the CAM assay

Figure 1 presents representative raw and skeletonized vascular networks observed in the CAM assay across treatments. The raw images illustrate differences in vascular density and branching, while the skeletonized images highlight the structural organization of the vessels, facilitating visualization of vessel length and branching patterns. These visual observations are consistent with the quantitative results obtained for the measured blood vessel parameters.

Summary of Statistical Tests on Different Blood Vessel Parameters Across Treatments

Statistical tests were performed to evaluate the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances across treatments and to determine the appropriate inferential analysis for each blood vessel parameter. Based on these results, suitable statistical tests were applied to assess differences among treatment groups.

Table 3. Summary of Statistical Tests on Different Blood Vessel Parameters Across Treatments

Parameters	Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)	Homogeneity Test (Levene Statistic)	Test Used	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Blood Vessels Count	Normal	Not Homogeneous	Welch ANOVA	0.110	Not Significant
Blood Vessels Length	Not Normal	Not Homogeneous	Kruskal – Wallis test	0.034	Not Significant
Branching Points	Not Normal	Not Homogeneous	Kruskal – Wallis test	0.265	Not Significant
Blood Vessel Area	Not Normal	Not Homogeneous	Kruskal – Wallis test	0.212	Not Significant
Blood Vessel Density	Not Normal	Not Homogeneous	Kruskal – Wallis test	0.261	Not Significant
Average Vessel Diameter	Not Normal	Homogeneous	Kruskal – Wallis test	0.120	Not Significant

Statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.01$.

Table 3 showed that most blood vessel parameters did not meet the assumptions required for parametric testing. Non-parametric analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis test was applied for these parameters. Blood vessel counts satisfied normality but violated homogeneity, which was analyzed using Welch ANOVA, while average vessel diameter met both assumptions and was analyzed using one-way ANOVA. Despite observable differences in mean values across treatments, all parameters yielded *p*-values greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.01$), indicating no statistically significant differences among treatment groups. These findings suggest that the treatments, including *A. bunius* extract at varying concentrations, did not produce statistically significant effects on the measured blood vessel parameters under the experimental conditions. The lack of significance may be attributed to variability within groups, limited sample size, or insufficient treatment effect to produce measurable differences.

Conclusions

This study evaluated the phytochemical constituents and anti-angiogenic potential of *A. bunius* root extract using the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) assay. Qualitative phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, phenolics, saponins, steroids, and terpenoids, which are associated with various biological activities.

In the CAM assay, a decreasing trend in vascular parameters was observed with increasing concentrations of the extract. The highest concentration (1000 ppm) exhibited the lowest values in blood vessel count, length, branching points, vessel area, density, and diameter compared to the negative control, indicating a potential inhibitory effect on

angiogenesis. The positive control (Simvastatin) also showed reduced vascular development. However, statistical analysis revealed that these differences were not significant at $\alpha = 0.01$, indicating that the observed variations among treatments were not sufficient to establish a definitive anti-angiogenic effect under the experimental conditions. Despite the lack of statistical significance, the consistent downward trend in vascular parameters at higher concentrations suggests a possible dose-related biological response. *A. bunius* root extract demonstrates potential as a source of compounds with anti-angiogenic properties; however, its effects were not statistically confirmed in this study. Further investigations using larger sample sizes, optimized concentrations, and extended experimental conditions are recommended to elucidate its anti-angiogenic potential and underlying mechanisms better.

Contributions of Authors

The authors indicate equal contributions to each section. The authors reviewed and approved the final work.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

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